

Factors Affecting Online Purchase Decisions in Generation Z in Indonesia

Nerys Lourensius L Tarigan, Petra Surya Mega Wijaya, Yuyun Wahyuni, Siti Kusandhitasari Jayaningrum
Department of Manajement, Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Isti Ekatana Upaweda Yogyakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- Covid 19 pandemic that has happened in Indonesia since March 2020 affects a number of sales places that offer offline transactions a very significant decline because purchases are made online. Generation Z as a generation that grows and develops in the increasingly sophisticated internet technology era is more prevalent to use internet in finding information to buy products. This research aims to analyze the value perception influence, online trust, perceived risk, purchase intention and perceived benefits on the online purchasing decisions of generation Z in Indonesia. The influence of security, brand image, eWOM and perceived website quality on online trust and finally is the influence of perceived website quality on perceived benefits. To answer the purpose of the study, a questionnaire was distributed through a google form to a number of respondents who were included in the criteria for generation Z in Indonesia. The spread is in chains, namely through what up groups. The respondents who gave answers to the questionnaire shared were 227 people and from these answers, data processing was carried out using SEM. The results of data processing show that all hypotheses proposed can be supported. In addition, this research also provides suggestions for further research development.

Keywords:- Online Purchase Decisions, Online Trust, Perceived Risk, Purchase Intention, Perceived Benefit, Value Perception.

I. INTRODUCTION

A report of Katalog Badan Pusat Statistik DIY (2021) states that the DIY economy contracted by 2.69% until the end of 2020. This contraction clearly hits almost all business sectors in DIY, especially when the government implements PPKM level 4 which severely limited economic operational activities in DIY to reduce the positive number of Covid patients 19. Research conducted by Ngadi et al. (2020) states that at the end of April 2020 there are 15.6% layoffs, of which 1.8% are with severance pay and the rest without severance pay. The report of Katalog Badan Pusat Statistik (2020) states that there are 45.93% of respondents from e-commerce businesses appearing in the 2017-2019 range. This condition is something interesting to study further about consumer behavior in online purchases.

Online purchase decision is a consumer process in recognizing problems, finding information about products or brands, evaluating alternatives which then lead to purchasing

decisions (Mahliza, 2020). Mahliza (2020) states that what influences a person to make purchases on the internet is trust, where trust is influenced by three variables, namely brand image, security, and perceived risk. Hidayat et al. (2021) states that purchasing decisions on the internet are influenced by buying interest, value perception, and customer trust. Research conducted by Lăzăroiu et al. (2020) states that purchasing decisions on the internet are influenced by buying interest, value perception, and customer trust. A research conducted by Lăzăroiu et al. (2020) mentions online trust, perceived risk and purchase intention influence people to make purchases online. Setiyawan et al. (2019) states that online consumers in Indonesia are influenced by attitude, eWOM (electronic word of mouth), perceived benefits, trust, and perceived website quality. Based on research conducted by Mahliza (2020), Hidayat et al. (2021), Lăzăroiu et al. (2020), and Setiyawan et al. (2019), a research framework will be built to examine online consumer behavior in Indonesia.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

A. Online Purchase Decision

Online shopping is a transaction process carried out through media or intermediaries, namely in the form of online buying and selling sites or social networks that provide traded goods or services (Turban et al., 2015). E-commerce provides benefits for consumers to shop without time and place barriers because users can access and have the transaction on the site anytime and anywhere (Hidayat et al., 2021).

The current retail environment adopts cutting-edge and increasingly interactive technologies that depend on adequate connectivity and systems so that direct contact is increasingly being abandoned by consumers when making transactions. (Pantano & Gandini, 2017). During the current pandemic, when people tend to avoid direct contact, it is a challenge for organizations to innovate based on developments in information technology so that they can still access the products they sell. (Katalog Badan Pusat Statistik, 2020).

B. Value Perception on Online Purchase Decision

Value perception is an overall assessment of the benefits of a product from consumers based on what is received and what has been given (Lai, 2004 in Rahab et al., 2015). Value perception is a trade-off that is a major focus in marketing science, where value acts as the precise measure of

any exchange, whether it is appropriate or not. (Hidayat et al., 2021).

A number of studies try to link value perception to online purchase decisions. (Tapar et al., 2015) conducts research with a sample of management students in India who have conducted transactions online, found that value perception influences the formation of online purchase decisions. Hidayat et al. (2021) who conducts research on e-commerce consumers in Indonesia finds results that value perception has a strong influence on the formation of online purchase decisions. Another research conducted by (Rahab et al., 2015) also strengthens the finding that value perception has a strong influence on online purchase decisions. Based on the research findings, the hypotheses that are built are:

Hypothesis 1: It is suspected that value perception has a significant influence on online purchase decisions.

C. Online Trust on Online Purchase Decision

Trust is an important factor in influencing consumer behavior towards companies (Mahliza, 2020). Trust plays an important role in online transactions because consumers will not make online transactions if they do not trust the seller. However, trust issues that arise in online purchases occur because they cannot verify the product directly (Dachyar & Banjarnahor, 2017).

Trust is also an issue that needs to be considered by sellers because it relates to consumers in making purchasing decisions (Murwatiningsih & Apriliani, 2013). Consumers will decide to make purchases online if they feel that the seller can be trusted (Hidayat et al., 2021). Trust is the willingness of one party to be vulnerable to the actions of another party based on the expectation that the other party will take certain actions that are important to the party being trusted. (Setiyawan et al., 2019).

Trust is important for online transactions because buyers and sellers do not meet face to face, so if there is no trust it will harm one party or even both parties. A number of studies are concerned with trust being associated with online purchase decisions. The results of the study state that trust has a significant influence on the formation of online purchase decisions of consumers in Indonesia (Setiyawan et al., 2019; Hidayat et al., 2021; Mahliza, 2020). Based on the results of previous research, the hypothesis is:

Hypothesis 2: It is suspected that online trust has a significant influence on online purchase decisions.

D. Perceived Risk on Online Purchase Decision

Trust for online business actors represents consumer confidence in the ability of the business actors themselves, knowledge related to products, performance, adequacy of marketing, integrity, and payment procedures (Lăzăroiu et al., 2020). Risk is the potential for an adverse event due to the uncertainty of the occurrence of an event and this uncertainty is a condition that results in the growth of risks originating from these various activities. (Dewi & Tarigan, 2022). If consumer trust increases, it is likely to reduce the risk of online shopping and ultimately advance the view of the purpose of shopping made by consumers (Mahliza,

2020). Martin (2018) states that misuse of information is an obvious type of online risk, the adherence to privacy is often associated with reliance on end-user surveys.

Regarding the risks of conducting online transactions, a number of studies have been conducted to test online purchases. Research conducted by Mahliza (2020) and Lăzăroiu et al. (2020) proves that perceived risk has a strong influence on online purchase decisions. Based on the research findings, the hypothesis that is built is:

Hypothesis 3: It is suspected that perceived risk has a significant influence on online purchase decisions.

E. Purchase Intention on Online Purchase Decision

Purchase intention can be interpreted as the consumer's intention to engage in online purchases (Pasharibu et al., 2020). Consumers can show purchase intentions before making a purchase decision, and after these consumers have a stronger interest in buying a product, they will decide to buy the product in question. (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Purchase intention is a decision made by a customer after analyzing the reasons for buying a brand of a product (Shah et al., 2012 in Purwianti & Ricarto, 2018). Purchase intention can be used to test the implementation of new distribution channels to help managers determine whether the concept is feasible for further development and decide which geographic markets and consumer segments to target through these channels including online sales. (Peña-García et al., 2020).

The research conducted by Pasharibu et al. (2020) on online purchasers in Indonesia states that there is a significant influence between purchase intention and online purchase decision. The same findings are reinforced by research conducted by Peña-García et al. (2020) for cross-cultural online consumers in Colombia and research conducted by Lăzăroiu et al. (2020) in India. Based on these findings, the hypothesis built is:

Hypothesis 4: It is suspected that purchase intention has a significant influence on online purchase decisions.

F. Perceived Benefit on Online Purchase Decision

Perceived benefit can be interpreted as the consumer's perception of the overall quality or superiority of goods or services related to the intended intentions and expectations. Perceived benefits are the number of benefits that can meet consumer needs, especially for online purchases (Setiyawan et al., 2019). Not only does the Internet present a number of risks in online shopping, but also provides many advantages that change consumer perceptions to buy online. The perceived benefits are consumer trust and satisfaction with online transactions and consumer perceptions that online shopping is convenient, easy, has a wider variety of products and is less risky than conventional shopping. (Bhatti & Ur Rehman, 2019).

Based on this fact, a number of studies are conducted to examine the effect of perceived benefits on online purchase decisions. Research conducted by Setiyawan et al. (2019) proves that there is a strong influence of perceived benefits on online purchase decisions among consumers in Indonesia.

The results of these studies are also supported by Bhatti & Ur Rehman (2019) which tested on consumers in Pakistan. Based on these findings, the hypothesis made is:

Hypothesis 5: It is suspected that perceived benefits have a significant influence on online purchase decisions.

G. Security on Online Trust

Security is a key factor that concerns people about using the internet, especially online purchases, because all transactions made online require buyers to provide their personal data, while the internet environment cannot be said to be secure (Raman & Viswanathan, 2011). Online buyers hope that their personal information cannot be accessed freely by anyone except the website owner himself for the smooth running of the transaction so that it cannot be manipulated and used by irresponsible parties. (Mahliza, 2020). Consumers will trust the seller when they feel that the seller guarantees the security of their data (Irawan, 2018). Security policy is a set of rules defined in all security activities in each segment, such as domain security (online store website address security) which aims to provide security against the absence of fake or similar domains, data security of each customer's personal information in online stores which aims to provide a sense of security to consumers so that the confidentiality of personal data information is not leaked and misused by irresponsible parties, and the security created aims to give consumers confidence to make purchases through e-commerce. Indicators of security or safety in online stores in e-commerce consist of: confidentiality/privacy, management of personal data, and assurance of trust/security (Ardiansyah, 2015).

Research in the field of security related to online trust has been carried out by a number of researchers, including Raman & Viswanathan (2011) in Malaysia, Mahliza (2020), Irawan (2018), dan Ardiansyah (2015) in Indonesia. The results of these researchers state that security has a significant influence on online trust. Based on the results of this study, the hypothesis that was built is:

Hypothesis 6 : It is suspected that security has a significant influence on online trust.

H. Brand Image on Online Trust

Brand image is a perspective or thought or a consumer's perspective on the identity of a brand based on various assumptions and experiences while using the brand repeatedly (Rohmanuddin & Arif Suprayogo, 2022). Armstrong et al. (2019) argues that the image that is communicated can protect the company, especially products resulting from competition and build a market for a brand. A brand cannot be produced overnight; however, the company's words and actions should help in building a brand image. Brand image features should be a long term goal and an asset to drive business success. Mahliza (2020) and Rahman et al. (2020) state that brand image is a strong driver for the formation of trust in the minds of consumers in online purchases; the higher the brand image of a product or company, the higher the trust in the minds of consumers.

Research aimed at testing the effect of brand image on online trust has been carried out by a number of researchers, including Mahliza (2020) who takes a sample of online shop consumers in Indonesia, Chrysnaputra (2020) with a sample of Umrah service users in Malang, and Rahman et al. (2020) with a sample of online consumers in Malaysia. The results of research conducted by these researchers states that brand image has a strong influence on the formation of online trust. Based on the results of this study, the hypothesis presented is: *Hypothesis 7: It is suspected that brand image has a significant influence on online trust.*

I. E-WOM (Electronic-Word of Mouth) on Online Trust

Schiffman et al. (2012) in Ernawati (2021) argues that communication also connects consumers with their social environment, namely marketing communications originating from companies and originating from consumers. E-WOM activities can provide negative or positive statements made by actual, potential or previous consumers about products or companies which are available to many people and institutions via the internet (Setiyawan et al., 2019). The existence of the internet creates a new paradigm in communication and word of mouth is the beginning of the emergence of electronic word of mouth (Erkan & Evans, 2016). The growth of the internet has led to its use to search for information about groceries on online platforms resulting in the emergence of e-WOM (Rahman et al., 2020). Online networks such as social networks, discussion forums and consumer review sites are being explored by more and more people to share experiences and information about products and services. Customers rely on e-WOM when seeking information before making a purchase decision compared to traditional media such as TV commercials, radio, personal selling and print advertising.

The belief that e-WOM has a large impact on online trust has prompted a number of studies to be conducted. Setiyawan et al. (2019) tries to do this research for respondent settings in Indonesia with the result that it is proven that e-WOM has a strong influence on the formation of online trust. Rahman et al. (2020) also gives the same results as respondents from consumers in Malaysia. With these results, this hypothesis is built.

Hypothesis 8: It is suspected that e-WOM has a significant effect on online trust.

J. Perceived Website Quality on Online Trust

Perceived website quality can be defined as the perception of internet users about the design of a website where the site is a place where group buying experiences are carried out (Qalati et al., 2021). Perceived website quality can be measured based on simple, smooth, reliable and effective website design and processes (Al-Debei et al., 2015). According to Al-Qeisi et al. (2014), perceived website quality can be divided into 4 parts; first, the technical dimension (security, search facilities, site availability, valid links, personalization or customization, page loading speed, interactivity, and ease of access); the second is general content (content usability, completeness, clarity, sophistication, conciseness, and accuracy); the third is specific content (contact information, general company

information, product/service details, consumer policies, and customer support), and the last is appearance (attraction, organization, use of the right fonts, colors, and the use of the right multimedia). Studies conducted by Septiari (2018) shows that consumer perceptions about perceived website quality online shopping have an impact on consumer perceptions about the benefits that can be obtained by using the website. The higher the perceived quality forms a positive impression of the website, the online consumers tend to buy from online sites they trust because they recognize the quality of the products and services provided.

It is believed that perceived website quality also has an influence on online trust and perceived benefits. This belief is based on research conducted oleh Setiyawan et al. (2019), Septiari (2018), and Sudiyono & Chairy (2017). Based on the results of this study, the hypothesis is:

Hypothesis 9: It is suspected that perceived website quality has a significant effect on online trust.

Hypothesis 10: It is suspected that perceived website quality has a significant effect on perceived benefits.

K. Research Framework

Based on the hypothesis that has been built, the research’s framework is as on Model 1.

Fig 1. Research Model

Source: Mahliza (2020), Hidayat et al. (2021), Lăzăroiu et al. (2020) Setiyawan et al. (2019).

III. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Population and Sampling Techniques

➤ **Population**

Population is the total collection of elements that are expected to be used for various purposes (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). Based on the research respondents who will be examined, the population of this study is all Indonesian residents who meet the criteria for generation Z, or were born from 1995 to 2010, namely (1) the generation that grows and develops when the internet is very advanced, (2) behavior generation Z who are more friendly to technology, especially the internet, (3) are used to making purchases online.

➤ **Sampling Technique**

The sample can be interpreted as a selection of several elements in the population which can be used to make a conclusion regarding the population (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). The sampling technique used is systematic sampling, namely random sampling but with a number of certain criteria. The criteria for research respondents are (1) Indonesian residents born from 1995 to 2010, (2) have made purchases online. The number of samples taken is 200 respondents because it relates to the hypothesis testing tool that will be used in order to produce good data processing.

B. Data Collection

This study uses primary data, namely data taken directly from the respondents through their answers to the questionnaire and then processing the data is done statistically, both for testing the research questionnaire and testing the hypothesis.

The questionnaire distributed consists of two major parts, namely (1) the characteristics of the respondents consisting of gender, education, monthly expenses, and occupation, (2) questions relating to all research variables. Specifically for questions about research variables, it will be measured using a Likert scale, with 5 answer choices, namely strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree.

The distribution of the questionnaire will use the Google form which is distributed to a number of WhatsApp groups that match the criteria of research respondents. In an effort to get respondents who match the research criteria, preliminary questions will be given, namely (1) nationality, (2) have they ever made an online purchase, (3) age. If all of these initial questions match the respondent's criteria then the answers from these respondents will be stored for statistical research data processing, but if any of the criteria do not meet then the respondent's answers will not be included in statistical data processing.

C. Questionnaire Test

➤ Validity test

The validity of a measuring instrument shows the extent to which a measuring instrument can measure what it is supposed to measure (Cooper & Schindler, 2014). The method used to test the validity of the research questionnaire is confirmatory factor analysis based on questionnaires that have been used in previous studies. An indicator can be said to be valid if it has a factor loading of at least 0.5 (Hair Jr. et al., 2013). The validity testing uses the structural equation model (SEM).

➤ Reliability Test

This test aims to test the consistency of the indicators used in the study. The test uses the standard Cronbach's alpha coefficient which shows results greater than or equal to 0.70 (Hair Jr. et al., 2013).

D. Hypothesis Testing

The research hypothesis testing uses a structural equation model (SEM) because the research model built is tiered or the independent variable can also become the dependent variable by looking at the causal relationship. The

tests use SEM that is not only test the causal relationship between research variables, but can also test the fit of the research model. The criteria for a model that can be said to be fit include (1) the chi-square value > 0.05, (2) RMSEA < 0.08, (3) NFI > 0.9, (4) CFI > 0.9, (5) GFI > 0.9, (6) AGFI > 0.9, dan (7) TLI > 0.95 (Sarwono, 2010).

➤ Research result

The research questionnaire is distributed to a number of WA groups which are the research targets using the Google form. A total of 227 data are received and can be used for data processing because they meet the criteria needed in this study.

E. Questionnaire Test

➤ Validity test

From the data as many as 227 are used for validity testing. Research indicators can be declared valid if they have a minimum loading factor of 0.5 (Sekaran, 2003; Hair Jr. et al., 2013). Process the data for validity testing using the AMOS program. The image of validity test is as shown in Figure 2.

Fig 2. Validity Test

Based on the validity test data processing, it can be presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Validity Test Results

Indicator	Estimated	Indicator	Estimated	Indicator	Estimated	Indicator	Estimated
S1	0.805	EW3	0.706	OT1	0.511	PI3	0.742
S2	0.810	EW4	0.625	OT2	0.792	PI4	0.640
S3	0.721	PWQ1	0.716	OT3	0.659	PB1	0.867
S4	0.639	PWQ2	0.767	OT4	0.662	PB2	0.772
BI1	0.560	PWQ3	0.757	PR1	0.586	PB3	0.655
BI2	0.799	PWQ4	0.577	PR2	0.758	PB4	0.657
BI3	0.619	VP1	0.618	PR3	0.713	OPD1	0.793
BI4	0.748	VP2	0.784	PR4	0.751	OPD2	0.856
EW1	0.575	VP3	0.885	PI1	0.814	OPD3	0.734
EW2	0.769	VP4	0.830	PI2	0.853	OPD4	0.573

Based on Table 1, it can be seen that all the indicators used have met the minimum standard of validity test, namely 0.5 or it can be said that all research indicators are valid.

➤ Reliability Test

The next process after the validity test is to test the reliability. The standard used is Cronbach's alpha coefficient. A research variable meets a reliable standard if it has a Cronbach's alpha coefficient value greater than or equal to 0,70 (Hair Jr. et al., 2013). The results of the reliability test are presented as followed :

Table 2 Reliability Test Results

Variable	Alpha Value
Security (S)	0.822
Brand Image (BI)	0.704
E-WOM (EW)	0.790
Perceived Website Quality (PWQ)	0.782
Value Perception (VP)	0.790
Online Trust (OT)	0.748
Perceived Risk (PR)	0.784
Purchase Intention (PI)	0.839
Perceived Benefit (PB)	0.717
Online Purchase Decision (OPD)	0.825

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that all variables have a Cronbach's alpha value greater than 0.7 or it can be said to fulfill the reliability test.

F. Hypothesis Test

➤ Evaluation of the Goodness of Fit Criteria

SEM analysis cannot be a single statistical test tool to test the level of suitability of the model. Therefore, several

indices are used as indicators of suitability together, namely χ^2 - Chi-Square, RMSEA, GFI, AGFI, TLI, CFI, and NFI. Based on the results of calculating the goodness of fit criteria from the estimated model, it is presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Goodness of Fit Model

Goodness of fit index	Critical Value	Index	Description
χ^2 -Chi-Square	expected small	1447.179	
χ^2 -Significance probability	≥ 0.05	0.061	Good
Relative χ^2 (CMIN/DF)	≤ 2.00	1.998	Good
GFI	≥ 0.90	0.971	Good
AGFI	≥ 0.90	0.927	Good
TLI	≥ 0.95	0.963	Good
CFI	≥ 0.90	0.973	Good
NFI	≥ 0.90	0.931	Good
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.073	Good

The value is 1447.179 with a significance level of 0.061. It can be said that this research model is statistically acceptable because it produces good goodness of fit on all standardized criteria.

➤ Evaluation of Causality Relations

The following is a picture of hypothesis testing using the AMOS program.

Fig 3. Hypothesis Testing

The causality relationship can be stated to be significant if the estimated parameter values of the two constructs have C.R. values greater than or equal to 1.96 with a significance level of 0.05 (5%) or C.R. is greater or equal to 2.56 for a

significance level of 0.01 (1%), whereas if the C.R. is smaller than 1.96, it has a weak causality relationship.

Based on these criteria, the results of the regression weight calculation for the model will be presented in Table 4.

Table 4 Structural Equation Model – Regression Weights

Description	CR
Value Perception (VP) → Online Purchase Decision (OPD)	6.098*
Online Trust (OT) → Online Purchase Decision (OPD)	4.646*
Perceived Risk (PR) → Online Purchase Decision (OPD)	- 2.376**
Purchase Intention (PI) → Online Purchase Decision (OPD)	8.647*
Perceived Benefit (PB) → Online Purchase Decision (OPD)	3.383*
Security (S) → Online Trust (OT)	3.810*
Brand Image (BI) → Online Trust (OT)	2.901*
E-WOM (EW) → Online Trust (OT)	4.489*
Perceived Website Quality (PWQ) → Online Trust (OT)	3.222*
Perceived Website Quality (PWQ) → Perceived Benefit (PB)	6.952*

Description: * significant at the 0.01 level

** significant at the 0.05 level

IV. DISCUSSION

A. The Effect of Value Perception on Online Purchase Intention

Based on data processing using AMOS, a CR value of 6,952 is obtained or greater than 2.56 or significant at the 1% level so that it can be said that value perception has a very strong influence on online purchase intention. From these findings, hypothesis 1 is supported. These results are in line with the results of research conducted by Tapar et al. (2015), Hidayat et al. (2021), and Rahab et al. (2015).

Generation Z in Indonesia considers that there is value in making purchases online. The stronger the perceived value, the stronger the desire to make purchases online.

B. The Effect of Online Trust on Online Purchase Intention

Online trust has a strong and significant influence on online purchase intention because it has a CR value of 4,646 or is significant at the 1% level. Based on this, hypothesis 2 is supported. The same results also occur in research conducted by Setiyawan et al. (2019), Hidayat et al. (2021), Mahliza (2020).

From these findings, it can be concluded that the higher the level of trust in online transactions, the higher the desire to make transactions online.

C. The Effect of Perceived Risk on Online Purchase Intention

The CR value of -2,376 on the effect of perceived risk on online purchase intention shows a strong influence, so hypothesis 3 is supported. This finding is in line with research conducted by Mahliza (2020) and Lăzăroiu et al. (2020).

Risk factors are a strong consideration for consumers to make online transactions. A number of incidents involving consumers being deceived when making online transactions have made consumers more careful in making transactions. Consumers will seek complete information before deciding to transact. The higher the risk understanding and the ability to minimize it, the higher the desire to make online transactions.

D. The Effect of Purchase Intention on Online Purchase Intention

Purchase intention has a strong and significant influence on online purchase intention because it has a CR value of 8,647 or is significant at the 1% level so that hypothesis 4 is supported. These results also support the results of research conducted by Peña-García et al. (2020) and Lăzăroiu et al. (2020).

When generation Z in Indonesia want to transact, not only they look at it from an offline purchase perspective, but they also see if it has an impact on online purchases. When consumers need a product, they will try to find it on a number of platforms to get the product they want. The higher their desire to get the product, the higher their desire to make online transactions.

E. The Effect of Perceived Benefit on Online Purchase Intention

Based on data processing, it shows that perceived benefit has a significant influence on online purchase intention because it has a CR value of 3,383, so it can be concluded that hypothesis 5 is supported. This result is also in line with the results of research conducted by Setiyawan et al. (2019) and Bhatti & Ur Rehman (2019).

Someone in buying a product wants an advantage from the product he buys. Through testimonials given by people around and on websites that are positive, it will make consumers more willing to make transactions online.

F. The Effect of Security on Online Trust

Security also has a strong influence on online trust because it has a CR value of 3,810 or is significant at the 1% level so that it can be said that hypothesis 6 is supported and in line with research conducted by Raman & Viswanathan (2011), Mahliza (2020), Irawan (2018), and Ardiansyah (2015).

The security of personal data and goods purchased by consumers during online transactions is important for these consumers because the more secure their personal data is, the higher their trust in online purchases will be.

G. The Effect of Brand Image on Online Trust

Brand image has a CR value of 2,901 on online trust or it can be said that brand image has a strong influence on online trust. These results conclude that hypothesis 7 is supported. Research conducted by Mahliza (2020), Chrystaputra (2020) and Rahman et al.(2020) strengthen the results of this study.

Consumers when buying a product will choose a website that has a reputation for good transactions so far marked by high and positive consumer reviews. If a website has a good reputation, the higher the consumer's trust in the provider.

H. The Effect of E-WOM on Online Trust

E-WOM is proven to have a significant effect on online trust because it has a CR value of 4,489 or is significant at the 1% level, so it can be said that hypothesis 8 is supported. This finding is in line with the findings by Setiyawan et al. (2019) and Rahman et al. (2020).

When a consumer buys a product, the first thing he does is reading the reviews given by consumers who have made online transactions before. These reviews are very easy to find from sites that sell online. Through reviews given by previous consumers who have made transactions and they are satisfied, the higher consumer confidence will be in making online transactions on a site.

I. The Effect of Perceived Website Quality on Online Trust

Hypothesis 9 is supported because the research results state that perceived website quality has a significant effect on online trust because it has a CR value of 3.222. This finding is in line with the results of research conducted by Setiyawan et al. (2019), Septiari (2018), and Sudiyono & Chairy (2017). All this time, online sales providers are competing to make their websites more attractive and make it easier for consumers to find the product they want and how to transact if they are going to make a purchase. The better an online sales site, the positive impact it will have on consumers to trust the provider's reputation more.

J. The Effect of Perceived Website Quality on Perceived Benefit

The last hypothesis is also supported because the effect of perceived website quality on perceived benefits has a CR value of 6,952 or is significant at the 1% level. This finding strengthens the findings made by Setiyawan et al. (2019), Septiari (2018), and Sudiyono & Chairy (2017).

The appearance of a good and easy-to-understand site makes it easier for consumers to find the type of product to buy or at least it will be easier for them to see the products being sold, just like consumers walking around the mall to see the products being sold. Providers will further strengthen the quality of their website so that consumers will increasingly benefit from the site.

V. CONCLUSION & SUGGESTION

➤ Conclusion

Based on the results of data processing using AMOS, this study can be concluded as follows:

- The first hypothesis which says that value perception has a significant influence on online purchase decisions can be supported.
- The second hypothesis which says that online trust has a significant influence on online purchase decisions can be supported.

- The third hypothesis, namely that perceived risk has a significant influence on online purchase decisions, can be supported.
- The fourth hypothesis which is suspected that purchase intention has a significant influence on online purchase decisions can be supported.
- The fifth hypothesis, namely that perceived benefits have a significant influence on online purchase decisions, can be supported.
- The sixth hypothesis which says that security has a significant influence on online trust can be supported.
- The seventh hypothesis which is suspected that brand image has a significant influence on online trust can be supported.
- The eighth hypothesis, namely that e-WOM has a significant influence on online trust, can be supported.
- The ninth hypothesis, namely that perceived website quality has a significant influence on online trust, can be supported.
- The tenth hypothesis, namely that perceived website quality has a significant influence on perceived benefits, can be supported.

➤ Suggestion

- This study uses closed questions for respondents or questions only use a questionnaire with predetermined answer choices. It would be better if, in further research, respondents are given the right to provide a number of opinions regarding online purchases because there is a possibility that they will get a number of more interesting answers.
- The questionnaire is distributed using the Google form so that there is no direct interaction between the researcher and the respondent who gives his opinion. The weakness of this method is that respondents may answer questions that do not meet the criteria set out in this study.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Al-Debei, M. M., Akroush, M. N., & Ashouri, M. I. (2015). Consumer attitudes towards online shopping: The effects of trust, perceived benefits, and perceived web quality. *Internet Research*, 25(5), 707–733. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IntR-05-2014-0146>
- [2]. Al-Qeisi, K., Dennis, C., Alamanos, E., & Jayawardhena, C. (2014). Website design quality and usage behavior: Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology. *Journal of Business Research*, 67(11), 2282–2290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2014.06.016>
- [3]. Ardiansyah. (2015). An Analysis of Security and Service Quality Toward Purchase Decision on E-Commerce And Its Implications Of Consumer Loyalty. *International Conference On Information Technology And Business*, August, 250–258.
- [4]. Armstrong, G., Kotler, P., Harker, M., & Brennan, R. (2019). *Marketing: An Introduction*, 4e. Pearson Education Limited.
- [5]. Bhatti, A., & Ur Rehman, S. (2019). Perceived Benefits and Perceived Risks Effect on Online Shopping Behavior With the Mediating Role of Consumer

- Purchase Intention in Pakistan. *International Journal of Management Studies*, 26(1), 33–54. <https://doi.org/10.32890/ijms.26.1.2019.10512>
- [6]. Chrysnaputra, R. D. (2020). Pengaruh Brand Image dan Trust terhadap Purchase Intention pada Jasa Umroh di Malang. *Al-Iqtishod: Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah*, 2(1), 68–89. <http://ejournal.iaiskjmalang.ac.id/index.php/iqtis/article/view/146>
- [7]. Cooper, D. R., & Schindler, P. S. (2014). Business Research Methods. In *Proceedings of the Annual Reliability and Maintainability Symposium*. The McGraw-Hill.
- [8]. Dachyar, M., & Banjarnahor, L. (2017). Factors Influencing Purchase Intention towards Consumer-to-Consumer e-Commerce. *Intangible Capital*, 13(5), 946–966. <https://doi.org/10.3926/ic.1119>
- [9]. Dewi, S. K., & Tarigan, A. A. (2022). Pengaruh Religiusitas, Risiko, Penanganan Keluhan Konsumen Terhadap Keputusan Penggunaan Shopee Paylater Dengan Minat Sebagai Variabel Intervening. *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Bisnis Dan Inovasi*, 9(3), 1544–1560. [10.35794/jmbi.v9i3.44486](https://doi.org/10.35794/jmbi.v9i3.44486)
- [10]. Erkan, I., & Evans, C. (2016). The Influence of eWOM in Social Media on Consumers' Purchase Intentions: An Extended Approach to Information Adoption. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 61(March), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.03.003>
- [11]. Ernawati, N. (2021). Stimulus Iklan, Positive Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM) dan Belanja Impulsif: Dampak Mediasi Motif Hedonis Pembelanja Online. *INOBI: Jurnal Inovasi Bisnis Dan Manajemen Indonesia*, 4(3), 346–360. <https://doi.org/10.31842/jurnalino.4i3.188>
- [12]. Hair Jr., J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E. (2013). Multivariate Data Analysis. In *Polymers*. Pearson Education Limited.
- [13]. Hidayat, A., Wijaya, T., Ishak, A., & Endi Catyanadika, P. (2021). Consumer Trust as the Antecedent of Online Consumer Purchase Decision. *Information (Switzerland)*, 12(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/info12040145>
- [14]. Irawan, I. A. (2018). Effect of Trust, Convinience, Security and Quality of Service on Online Purchase Decision (Consumer Case Study in Tangerang Selatan Area). *Jurnal Ekonomi*, 23(1), 114–122. <https://doi.org/10.24912/je.v23i1.337>
- [15]. Katalog Badan Pusat Statistik. (2020). *Statistik E-Commerce 2020* (Vol. 21, Issue 1). <http://journal.um-surabaya.ac.id/index.php/JKM/article/view/2203>
- [16]. Katalog Badan Pusat Statistik DIY. (2021). *Analisis Pertumbuhan dan Perubahan Struktur Perekonomian Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta Sebelum dan Selama Masa Pandemi Covid-19: Pendekatan 54 Kategori dan Sub-Kategori Usaha*. <https://yogyakarta.bps.go.id/publication/2021/04/28/814d6f552338d3ef9649bb30/analisis-pertumbuhan-dan-perubahan-struktur-perekonomian-daerah-istimewa-yogyakarta-sebelum-dan-selama-masa-pandemi-covid-19---pendekatan-54-kategori-dan-sub-kategori-usaha.html>
- [17]. Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2016). Marketing Management. In *Pearson Education Limited*.
- [18]. Lăzăroi, G., Neguriță, O., Grecu, I., Grecu, G., & Mitran, P. C. (2020). Consumers' Decision-Making Process on Social Commerce Platforms: Online Trust, Perceived Risk, and Purchase Intentions. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11(May), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00890>
- [19]. Mahliza, F. (2020). Consumer Trust in Online Purchase Decision. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, 6(2), 142–149. <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra4022>
- [20]. Martin, K. (2018). The Penalty for Privacy Violations: How Privacy Violations Impact Trust Online. *Journal of Business Research*, 82(September 2017), 103–116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.08.034>
- [21]. Murwatiningsih, & Apriliani, E. P. (2013). Apakah Kepercayaan Konsumen Lebih Efektif Daripada Risiko dan Harga? Whether Customer Trust Is More Effective Than The Risk and Price? *Jurnal Dinamika Manajemen*, 4(2), 180–187. <http://jdm.unnes.ac.id>
- [22]. Ngadi, N., Meliana, R., & Purba, Y. A. (2020). Dampak Pandemi Covid-19 Terhadap Phk Dan Pendapatan Pekerja Di Indonesia. *Jurnal Kependudukan Indonesia*, 29(2), 43–48. <https://doi.org/10.14203/jki.v0i0.576>
- [23]. Pantano, E., & Gandini, A. (2017). Exploring the Forms of Sociality mediated by Innovative Technologies in Retail Settings. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 77, 367–373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2017.02.036>
- [24]. Pasharibu, Y., Soerijanto, J. A., & Jie, F. (2020). Intention to buy, interactive marketing, and online purchase decisions. *Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis*, 23(2), 339–356. <https://doi.org/10.24914/jeb.v23i2.3398>
- [25]. Peña-García, N., Gil-Saura, I., Rodríguez-Orejuela, A., & Siqueira-Junior, J. R. (2020). Purchase intention and purchase behavior online: A cross-cultural approach. *Heliyon*, 6(6). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04284>
- [26]. Purwianti, L., & Ricarto, T. (2018). Analisa Faktor-Faktor yang Mempengaruhi Purchase Intention pada Pengguna Smartphone di Batam. *Jurnal Manajemen Maranatha*, 18(1), 41–56. <https://doi.org/10.28932/jmm.v18i1.1095>
- [27]. Qalati, S. A., Vela, E. G., Li, W., Dakhan, S. A., Hong Thuy, T. T., & Merani, S. H. (2021). Effects of perceived service quality, website quality, and reputation on purchase intention: The mediating and moderating roles of trust and perceived risk in online shopping. *Cogent Business and Management*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2020.1869363>
- [28]. Rahab, Handayani, S. R., & Tri Nawarini, A. (2015). Peran Perceived Value dan Kepuasan Pelanggan dalam Upaya Membangun Loyalitas Pengguna Kartu Seluler. *Media Ekonomi Dan Manajemen*, 30(1), 76.
- [29]. Rahman, M. A., Abir, T., Yazdani, D. M. N.-A., Hamid, A. B. A., & Mamun, A. Al. (2020). Brand Image, eWOM, Trust and Online Purchase Intention of Digital Products among Malaysian Consumers. *Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture & Technology*, XII(III), 4935–4946. <https://doi.org/10.37896/jxat12.03/452>

- [30]. Raman, A., & Viswanathan, A. (2011). Web Services and E-Shopping Decisions: A Study on Malaysian E-Consumer. *IJCA Special Issue on "Wireless Information Networks & Business Information System" WINBIS, February 2011*, 54–60.
- [31]. Rohmanuddin, & Arif Suprayogo, H. (2022). Pengaruh Brand Image dan Harga terhadap Keputusan Pembelian di Masa Pandemi Covid 19 (Studi Kasus pada Bisnis Ritel Pakaian "Sting" Cabang Kedoya Green Garden). *Jurnal Bina Manajemen*, 10(2), 78–89.
- [32]. Sarwono, J. (2010). Pengertian Dasar Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Bisnis*, 10(3), 173–182.
- [33]. Sekaran, U. (2003). *Research Methods for Business : A Skill Building Approach*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. All.
- [34]. Septiari, E. D. (2018). The Effect of eWOM as Mediation of Website Quality and Trust. *Kinerja*, 22(2), 142–155. <https://doi.org/10.24002/kinerja.v22i2.1809>
- [35]. Setiyawan, E., Nuryakin, & Susanto. (2019). Antecedent of Consumer Attitudes Toward Online Shopping in Indonesia. *The International Journal of Business Management and Technology*, 3(2), 52–61.
- [36]. Sudiyono, F., & Chairy, C. (2017). Pengaruh Website Quality terhadap Perceived Trust dan Dampaknya pada Repurchase Intention pada Website Matahari Mall. *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis Dan Kewirausahaan*, 1(1), 38–46. <https://doi.org/10.24912/jmbk.v1i1.4746>
- [37]. Tapar, A. V., Subhash, A., Kumar, S., & Shameem, M. (2015). Examining Role of Perceived Customer in Online Shopping. *Indian Journal of Economics & Business*, 14(2), 235–244.
- [38]. Turban, E., King, D., Lee, J. K., Liang, T.-P., & Turban, D. C. (2015). Electronic commerce. In *Springer International Publishing Switzerland 2015*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0256090920040313>